

Katy KAKOON

doctorandă, Universitatea Pedagogică de Stat
I. Creangă din Chișinău

A profile of the teacher working with students at risk

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Abstract: The article addresses the issues of the teacher's profile working with students at risk. The expectations from such teachers are enormous. One of the basic presumptions is that the educational characters at school have abilities and must be most significant in building up emotional stability and decreasing anxiety and dangers for students at risk. Accordingly, the teacher is expected to present an educational character that goes beyond his traditional role as an imparter

of knowledge; the teacher has a personal educational side. The teacher's ability to relate personally with the pupil is of great importance so that the pupil will learn to interact in the world – both socially and within the family. All these aspects create a background for practical interventions.

Keywords: teacher's profile, new paradigm, students at risk, education.

Rezumat: Articolul abordează profilul profesorului care lucrează cu elevii aflați în situații de risc. Așteptările de la asemenea profesori sunt enorme. Una dintre prezumțiile de bază este că actorii educaționali din școală posedă abilități și capacități pentru constituirea stabilității emoționale și diminuarea anxietății și a pericolelor pentru elevii aflați în situații de risc. În consecință, se așteaptă ca profesorul să prezinte un caracter educațional care depășește rolul tradițional de furnizor de cunoștințe; profesorul are o latură educativă personală. Capacitatea profesorului de a relaționa personal cu elevul este de mare importanță, astfel încât elevul să învețe să interacționeze în lumea înconjurătoare – atât în plan social, cât și în familie. Toate aceste aspecte creează fundalul intervențiilor practice.

Cuvinte-cheie: profilul profesorului, noua paradigmă, elevi în situații de risc, educație.

Introduction. The postmodern era is characterized by change and popularism, which – once again – raises the question of the ideal teacher's character in relation to the teaching curriculum, especially when there is a need for the education system to impart skills for this constantly changing environment. Such training includes, among other things, teacher training for specific student populations. Our research concerns teachers working with students at risk.

The interest of researchers in the education system has increased in the recent decades, focusing on many aspects and different categories of students, including those at risk. Several factors were found to be significant, among which the structure of the organization, staff-student relationships, and non-organizational resources. Many authors recognize that the most important player in the process of education is the teacher.

The basic idea of our research is to develop a comprising teacher, someone who is flexible and can adapt to the rapid changes of today. A comprising teacher should adjust to the conditions and the special needs of pupils at risk. In the past, a teacher's role was merely to transfer knowledge and expertise, and he expected the pupils to be obedient, according to the psycho-social approach [4].

Our research finds whether it is possible to create an inclusive teacher profile for at-risk students, one that would provide a successful experience through internal motivation.

The new approaches to teachers' profile. Some authors, such as Kaplan and Maehr [1], describe the school as a place characterized by a certain culture that emphasizes values, norms, and beliefs that pass to pupils at risk and teachers about what is important and valued in school. While some schools emphasize excellence and high-ability demonstration as valuable things, other schools emphasize learning and understanding, and there are also schools with cultures that transmit dual messages, including these two meanings of educational practice [3]. This school culture can sometimes be a problem for individual teachers who try in their classes to change the emphasis on motivation. For example, a teacher who is trying to give learning tasks considering the interests of the pupils at risk may come across difficulties arising from the school's emphasis on excellence in exams.

The expectations from a teacher of pupils at risk are based on the assumption that educational images at school can and should be significant figures in order to build the mental resilience of these pupils

and to prevent their deterioration. It is expected that this teacher would not only be an educational figure as per the old paradigm (transferring knowledge), but should grant a personal educational treatment, would know how to develop an optimal close relationship with the child, a good personal relationship that will cure the child based on his personal world and make him succeed in learning. The teacher is supposed to be attentive and to implement the tasks coming from the organization (outside authority) as well as from his/her subjective authority (from his own being) [5].

The teachers who work in an environment of deep exclusion will suffer from a lack of esteem and lack of prestige. They experience dropout and see themselves as invisible just as their pupils at risk do. Throughout work with the teams and principals, we shall emphasize the parallel process of erasing the needs of the teacher as a person, and encourage the teachers to define verbally and clearly what they need as emotional support, acknowledgment, and appreciation.

A teacher who identifies with the weakness of the student experiences his weaknesses as insufferable; he perceives the experience as a disgusting one. Anger prevents him from separating vulnerability that comes from family, self-image, and absence of ability, making him accept the fact that he is 'stupid' and take the place of the student who is experiencing these difficulties.

One of the most significant achievements of the modern world in the field of education is the transition from education for the minority to education for the general population. This achievement has great significance in the field of culture, economy, and sociology. This transition was the main cause for the training of teachers in general and caused the evolution in defining the characters of teachers in particular.

From literature it appears that teachers have had an impact on pupils/students at all times: on their academic achievements and on their lives as adults. On winning the Nobel Prize for Literature Albert Camus addressed

these words to his teacher: "When I learned of my win, the first person I thought of, after my mother, was you. Without you, without the warm hand you offered to the small poor boy I was, without your guidance and your personal example, none of this would have occurred. This is my opportunity to say what you were and still are to me, to assure you that all your efforts, your hard work and generosity are still alive in the heart of your young pupil, and in spite of your age, I will always be appreciative".

These very moving words emphasize how significant the teacher's role is in the life of his pupils. Researchers have attempted to find the characteristics of the ideal teacher [6; 7]. Their goal was to measure and predict a teacher's success and efficiency through educational and teaching activities. We can see from relevant literature that the characteristics of the ideal teacher refer to his personality, beliefs and convictions, education, and teaching experience. The personality of the ideal teacher is expressed through personal initiative, communication skills, flexibility, pleasantness, patience, and congeniality. The beliefs and convictions of the ideal teacher are reflected in his teaching, while social skills are key elements of interactive education. The ideal teacher expresses education and teaching skills as differential knowledge: knowledge of the subjects that are taught as well as knowledge of teaching skills.

Based on several ideas reflected in different publications [2; 6; 7], we would like to propose a comparative analysis of a teacher's profile from the perspective of the "New Paradigm" vs "Old Paradigm" (Table 1). We completed the model with some suggestions (in italics), with a focus on the following: *An inclusive teacher for pupils at risk, who will impart a successful experience through internal motivation; Students/pupils at risk are encouraged, viewed as potential agents of change (in the school – adaptation strategies) etc.*

Table 1. *The teacher in the New Paradigm vs the Old Paradigm*

New Paradigm	Old Paradigm
The teacher supports and directs the pupil's course of study in helping him find his own sources of information.	The teacher as the source of information.
Employing multiple intelligences.	Partial ability and limited fitness to teach.
Individual-style teaching.	Standard teaching.
The role of teaching is to arouse curiosity.	The role of teaching is to transfer information.
Teaching is a process intended to enable entrepreneurship, to encourage, to direct, and to support the efficient self-learning and self-fulfillment of the pupil.	Teaching is based on transferring information in a disciplined manner.
Learning is a process of joy both for the pupil and the teacher.	Teaching aims at bringing the pupils to the standard required by exams.
Expertise in teaching is a process that continues throughout the whole of a teacher's carrier.	Teaching is a feasible role of transferring information.

Teaching is based on various sources: local and global.	The teacher is the only source of knowledge in the process of learning.
Cooperation between teachers on the Net.	Every teacher works individually.
Teaching opportunities are endless.	Teaching opportunities and sources are limited.
Teachers have both a local and an international vision.	Teachers have only school experience.
<i>Students/pupils at risk are encouraged, viewed as potential agent of changes (in the school – adaptation strategies).</i>	<i>Students/pupils at risk are stigmatized, viewed as a problem/barrier in the educational performance of the school.</i>
Cooperation between teachers and students on the Net.	Work is mostly based on literature.
Human rights-based approach: all students are equal, but different – with specific needs that should be taken into consideration.	Approach on formal equality: all students are equal for the teacher, taking into consideration the age specifics.
An inclusive teacher for pupils at risk, who will impart a successful experience through internal motivation.	

In our opinion, a good teacher has all the following characteristics:

- Personality: someone with personal and public courage, who behaves honestly, possesses empathic understanding, self-dignity, self-awareness, personal responsibility, creative imagination, playing and improvisation abilities, and a sense of humor.
- Professionalism: professional authority, an expert in various types of learning and teaching, a person with original thinking and creative curiosity, with the ability of rhetoric, capable of managing different learning situations.
- Pedagogy: the teacher is a personal example, he is an instructor, consultant, and assistant in learning, he develops the students' intellectual curiosity and motivation to learn and expresses his ideas in a simple and coherent way.

This is a theoretical model that was originally developed in order to give an answer to the special need of minorities. Later the model has been used in a variety of treatment contexts.

At the same time, instead of totally focusing on the needs of a person or of society, it is more advisable to choose to listen to the dynamic needs of both sides (inter-adaptation), by trying to adjust a solution to the person's needs in his meaningful context by moving on the scale from the individual to the community. This movement enables, in fact, an effective connection between the individual's uniqueness and the space where it can be expressed, through a dialogue of permanent search and adaptation to the evolution of the individual as well as by paying attention to changes in the environment – the solution granted to the individual will not harm the community and vice versa.

In conclusion: Literature shows that the ideal teacher is not identified in specific terms. Our research establishes that the ideal teacher is deserving, successful, ideal, good, and significant. We chose to deal

with the definition of the 'inclusive teacher', since the research aims to build schools where a model for the inclusive teacher can be used for the particular needs of at-risk students. These students lack the ability to adapt to their environment and lack faith in their surroundings. Their teachers are a buffer between themselves and the school and other significant adults in their lives and surroundings.

BIBLIOGRAPHICAL REFERENCES:

1. Kaplan A., Maehr M. L. The Contributions and Prospects of Goal Orientation Theory. In: Educational Psychology Review, Vol. 19, No 2, 2007, pp. 141-184.
2. Khan A. et al. Communication Skills of a Teacher and Its Role in the Development of the Students' Academic Success. In: Journal of Education and Practice, Vol. 8, No.1, 2017, pp. 18-21.
3. Maehr M.L., Midgley C. Enhancing Student Motivation: A Schoolwide Approach. In: Educational Psychologist, 26, 1991, pp. 399-427.
4. Mor F., Luria I. The Nurturing School: A Psychodynamic Approach. Jerusalem: JDC, Israel-Ashalim, 2014. 245 p.
5. Mor F., Bar Sh. The Psychosocial Approach: A Case Study in School Intervention and in Teacher Training. In: The International Journal of Interdisciplinary Social Sciences, Vol. 2, Nr. 2, 2007, pp. 35-62.
6. Reichel N., Arnon S. Three Portraits of Teachers in the Mirror of the Education Student: The Ideal Teacher, the Teacher of Teachers and the Image of the Student Him/Herself as a Teacher. In: Dapim, 40, 2005, pp. 23-58.
7. Yossifon M. Empowerment as Leading to Change and as Its Outcome: New Aspects in Professional Development in the School. In: Guri-Rosenblit S. (Ed.) Teachers in a Changing World. Tel Aviv: The Open University, 2004, pp. 38-73.